

THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION OF THE ICHAN KALA STATE MUSEUM-RESERVE AND SAMPLES OF HEADWEAR IN IT

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Abstract. *This article covers the history of the "Ichan Kala" State Museum-Reserve, collections of headwear stored in its collection, and its types. The number of applied art collections has been analyzed.*

Keywords: *"Ichan Kala" State Museum-Reserve, collections of applied art, taHYa, ethnography, national headwear.*

The "Ichan Kala" State Museum-Reserve, one of the oldest and most ancient museums in Uzbekistan, contains 58 ancient structures and historical buildings. 360 households have also been preserved on the territory of the open-air museum. A total of 19 permanent exhibitions are organized in the museum-reserve, among which exhibits reflecting the history, crafts, and applied arts of ancient Khorezm occupy a special place.

By Decree No. 616 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 30, 1967, the ancient part of the city of Khiva was declared a "Reserve" and had a separate administration. By Resolution No. 343 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated July 21, 1969, the museum was merged with the reserve, and the Khiva "Ichan Kala" State Historical and Architectural Museum-Reserve was established. This, in turn, laid the foundation for the museum's transformation into a major scientific institution in the future and placed the responsibility on museum staff to preserve and restore architectural monuments, open new museums, collect historical artifacts held by the population, study them scientifically, promote them, and pass them on to future generations in their original state.

The laureate of the State Prize, People's Artist Abdulla Boltayev, writer and playwright Yunus Yusupov, members of the Union of Journalists Madamin Yakubov and Anvar Ismoilov, and Honored Cultural Workers of Uzbekistan Sobirjon Yusupov and Nurmat Sherov made great contributions to the organization and development of the museum-reserve.

During the years of independence, a large number of original museum objects of numismatic, military-historical, ethnographic, zoological, botanical, and artistic nature were collected in the museums of Uzbekistan thanks to continuous collection activities. As part of the aforementioned initiatives, the 19 permanent exhibits of the "Ichan Kala" State Historical and Architectural Museum-Reserve illuminate and demonstrate the history of Ancient Khorezm from the past to the present day using ethnographic museum materials.

Currently, a total of 56,158 museum objects are stored in the collection of the "Ichan Kala" State Museum-Reserve, of which 39,699 are in the main fund and 16,448 are in the auxiliary fund. The museum objects are divided into 39 collections and are distributed across 5 funds: 1. The numismatic collection comprises 22,668 pieces. 2. The collection of manuscripts and documents consists of 5,418 pieces. 3. The ethnographic collection contains 4,849 pieces. 4. The collection

of photographs and photographic negatives includes 4,145 pieces. 5. The collection of fine art consists of 2,750 pieces. Over the past three years, scientific staff from the "Ichan Kala" State Museum-Reserve organized scientific expeditions to the districts of the region, collecting 874 museum materials on the history and ethnography of Khorezm, of which 438 were included in the main fund and 436 - in the scientific and auxiliary fund.

A plan of measures has been developed to preserve and promote the museum-reserve's exhibits. Exhibitions have been regularly updated, and museum collections have been enriched with exhibits. Work is being carried out to study the material heritage of the museum from a scientific perspective and promote it. Today, the State Museum-Reserve houses departments of Ancient Khorezm, History of the Khiva Khanate, Applied Arts, Khorezm Crafts, Nature, Avesto, History of Public Education, History of Khorezm Musical Art, History of Medicine, and History of Kiyat Village. A significant portion of the main and unique exhibits on the history of Khorezm are displayed in these exhibitions. In addition, an exhibition of fine arts and permanent exhibitions on Khorezm during the years of independence have been organized.

The exhibitions of Khorezm applied arts, located in the Madrasah of Islam Khoja, stand out for their uniqueness and priceless nature in "Ichan Kala." The museum exhibition was opened in 1983 to commemorate the 1200th anniversary of the birth of the great scholar and mathematician Al-Khorezmi. After 1991, the exhibition halls were reconstructed in the spirit of independence. About 400 samples of masterpieces of art are displayed at the Khorezm Exhibition of Applied Arts. As you stroll through the showrooms, you will enjoy the wonders created by human hands, the unique and refined works of art.

In particular, among the objects of applied art, national headwear is of special importance. The museum-reserve displays women's, men's, children's, and brides' skullcaps, *tahyas*, and many other national headwear. In the Folk Applied Arts Department, about 15 types of *tahyas* made of velvet, silk, and gold-embroidered fabrics with flat tops in the Khorezmian style are featured in the exposition. Their shape is predominantly round; some are made with paper or cotton padding, while others are prepared with a thick paper lining. Padded *tahyas* are sewn in the felt-embroidery style. For this, thin, long, and stiff strips were prepared using paper. These strips were attached to the back of the fabric and firmly pressed. Then, the separately sewn top and lower parts were joined together.

The ethnographic fund of the museum-reserve is extremely rich in headwear. The ethnographic fund first received headwear in 1967. Initially, there were 5 types, and today there are about 250 varieties.

According to the 2023 report on the museum fund's collection numbers, the applied art collections comprise 2,868 items. Based on the analysis results, the number of headwear pieces in the applied art collections occupies a significant place. Works of applied art were widely used in creating numerous museum exhibitions. National costumes stored in the museum were also extensively used in organizing the exhibition "Our National Costume - An Adornment of Our Values" held on March 18, 2023, at the Toshhovli Palace.

Headwear collections were widely utilized. At this exhibition, one can see textile products from the Khorezm oasis, including silk scarves, silk belts, women's jackets (chopons), women's dresses, *tahyas* (skullcaps), brides' skullcaps, men's chapans, and *chugirmas* (men's headdresses) that are unique to the region.

As part of implementing the decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Culture, the museum-reserve is incorporating innovative technologies in the museum sector. In particular, in 2020, the museum-reserve signed an agreement with the SmartChain company to introduce a new augmented reality system in the museum through the NazzAR platform. Representatives of the "SmartChain" company held negotiations with the museum-reserve administration and signed 6 projects. The augmented reality system is designed to provide visitors with modern interactive features when viewing museum exhibits, offering audio, video, and 3D content. An audio guide service has been established specifically in the applied arts department. This service allows visitors to obtain information about national headwear and costumes in four languages.

The use of this solution enables visitors to take independent "open-air" tours within the museum-reserve territory. Creating interactive monument maps allows visitors to extend their journey. By purchasing a set of monument cards, visitors can repeatedly access video, audio, and 3D content, and share their impressions with friends and acquaintances. The use of such cards helps attract attention to the museum, its exhibits, and exhibitions, as well as expand the audience. Creating 3D models and 3D scenes with moving and talking characters integrated into the museum space establishes a unique connection between time periods. A museum visitor, while inside the exposition, can point their smartphone in different directions to see scenes of life appear before them. For example, for the Khorezm craftsmanship exhibition, one can show how craftsmen worked on looms or spinning machines, the process of sewing headwear, or the process of trying on skullcaps online using a mobile application.

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